

RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT CHECKLIST

PLANNING

1. Identify the **type of data** you will be working on – more [here](#) and [here](#)
2. Always keep in mind the **FAIR principles** for research data management – more [here](#)
3. Check compliance with the rules on **ethical principles, privacy and intellectual property**
4. Identify the **metadata** that will be needed to describe your data – more [here](#)
5. Plan the **structure** you intend to give the data, organising them into datasets
6. Think about which **repository** to choose for **long-term preservation and sharing**
7. Write the first version of the **Data Management Plan (DMP)** – more [here](#)

In case, please contact the [Privacy and DPO Support Office](#), [Intellectual Property Office](#), [Ethics Committee](#)

- 6.1. Use a registry to search for repositories suitable for your data and to check their requirements (such as [re3data](#))
- 6.2. If there is a repository specific to your subject area, use that, if not choose the repository of your home institution (such as [Dataverse UNIMI](#)), or, as a last choice, a generalist repository
- 6.3. Choose a repository that: guarantees long-term data preservation, assigns a Persistent Identifier (e.g. DOI), allows metadata association, licensing, open (but controlled) access, and has a clear policy – more [here](#)

COLLECTION, PROCESSING AND ANALYSIS

8. Define a **standard methodology and processes** for data analysis and processing – use [electronic lab notebooks](#) and proceed to the [method pre-registration](#) if necessary
9. Store data in appropriate **storage spaces** in the medium term (e.g. OneDrive), providing **periodic backups**
10. Collect the documentation necessary to understand the data in a **README file**
11. Ensure **data quality** through methodical processes
12. Update the DMP

A **text document** where you should:

- 10.1. Explain the type of data, its origin, and the hierarchical relationships between data in the same dataset
- 10.2. Keep track of versions of data files as they are processed
- 10.3. Keep track of the nomenclatures adopted (and preferably choose standard ones)
- 10.4. Keep track of software, protocols and other tools used for data processing – more [here](#)

PRESERVATION AND SHARING

13. Assess what data needs to be deposited in the repository – more [here](#)
14. Check that you have all the necessary **requirements and permissions** for depositing and publishing
15. **Deposit your data in datasets** in the chosen repository
16. Remember to also deposit the **README file and other accompanying documentation** (e.g.: code, software, DMP)
17. Compile the **metadata** of your dataset comprehensively – the more you describe your data, the more other researchers will be able to understand and reuse it effectively
18. Assign a **licence** to your dataset, to indicate the terms of access and conditions for re-use – more [here](#)
19. **Publish** (or submit for review for publication) **the data produced by your research and share it!**

- 14.1. Who is the owner of the data and therefore has the right to publish it? Have you discussed the deposit of the data with the other (possible) members of the research group?
- 14.2. What are the requirements of the funding body?
- 14.3. What are the requirements of the chosen repository?
- 14.4. Are there any special permissions of project partners on the basis of the agreement?
- 14.5. Does your data incorporate re-used data from third parties?
- 14.6. Does your data contain anonymised or pseudo-anonymised personal information? – more [here](#) and [here](#)
- 14.7. Is your data commercially sensitive?
- 14.8. Have you obtained approval from the Ethics Committee?
- 14.9. Does your data comply with any other ethical principles and rules on privacy and intellectual property?

- 15.1. Make a final check on the quality of your data and the presence of errors or alterations in your data files – more [here](#)
- 15.2. Make sure the files are in [open and non-proprietary formats](#)
- 15.3. Check that the structure and nomenclatures of the dataset you are depositing conform to those stated in the README
- 15.4. Pay particular attention to the title you give to your dataset: it must be informative, clear, and correspond to a possible related publication – if you deposit your data in Dataverse UNIMI do not forget to check the [dedicated guidelines](#)

Include: **17.1.** A detailed description of the dataset, explaining its purpose, type and origin of the data, how it was collected and processed, any naming conventions used; **17.2.** The citation of any related publication; **17.3.** Domain-specific keywords; **17.4.** Reference to the funds that financed the project that produced the data; **17.5.** Reference to other material related to your dataset (e.g.: other datasets, publications, pre-recorded method, etc); **17.6.** The indication of any software (and its version) required to access the data

This checklist is generally inspired by similar documents from the [University of Bologna](#) and the [University of Cambridge](#).

The checklist was drawn up by Carolina Manfredini, Laura Giovinazzi, Margherita Criveller, data stewards of the University of Milan, in collaboration with the Performance, Quality Assurance, Evaluation and Open Science Policy Division – responsible for supporting all Open Science and research data management activities –, and is made available to the Unimi community, both on the website dedicated to [Research Data Management](#), and on the [Zenodo](#) page that Unimi dedicates to Open Science.

Our university supports the principles and actions in favour of open management of research data, an indispensable prerequisite for the reproducibility and validation of research, the transparency of processes and open access to the results of science, committing itself to applying the highest standards for their collection, archiving and preservation, as set out in the institutional [Policy on Research Data Management](#).

For support and clarification on research data management, FAIR principles, drafting a Data Management Plan (DMP), choosing a repository for storing and sharing research data, and sharing and anonymising sensitive data, please contact rdm@unimi.it

For support and clarification on the use of the University repository, Data@UNIMI – built on the Dataverse open source software –, please contact dataverse@unimi.it

